

A 'Lag-Lead' method of trading and analysis

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Price volatility in equities is partly caused by variable ownership intervals among investors; these may vary from minutes, to hours, days, and so on, not all obviously in action concurrently. An averaging window moving through price histories should show fluctuations caused by these variations.

Residuals off moving averages magnify these movements; two control parameters are available here: data interval width and mean placement; and placements can 'lag', 'lead', or be 'centered'; see graphic below.

Let's look at Apple (AAPL) stock as an example (in blue, top panel) - 1981 though early 2025 - in log-scale; the 'center' estimate (overlaid in red) tracks the data (in blue) as expected; interval width here was (long) 600 trading days. The lower panel shows the residuals off log-scales; some cycles are evident.

The 'lag-lead' strategy of the title is best explained by the images below; the strategy was applied to a section of the log-scaled AAPL stock from 1999-2002 using a (shorter) 30-day window.

Legend

Blue: AAPL Price data in log-scale

Black: **Lag** estimate

Red: **Lead** estimate

Magenta: $\text{Sign}(\text{Lag} - \text{Lead})$ shifted to fit in the plot (scaled and shifted elsewhere)

Periods of growth clearly coincided with the **Lag** dominating the **Lead**; so a trading strategy has emerged.

The first-difference of the estimate $\text{Sign}(\text{Lag} - \text{Lead})$ is overlaid on the data stream to serve as **Buy-Sell** markers; see image below. The **S** markers could, of course, be 'sell short' signals until the **Buy** signal comes up; and window lengths are at the investor's discretion.

Let's next examine the 'lag-lead' method in action on the DOW average (again in log-scale), around three calamitous events; the 1929 crash, the 1987 crash, and the 2007-2009 'subprime' financial crisis; see below.

First, the 1929 crash, a global catastrophe worsened by actions of the US Federal Reserve.

The lag-to-lead cross-over occurred well before the disastrous events towards the end of 1929; although some courageous investors got back in briefly after 1930, the action until mid-1932 appeared mostly a pure 'short-sell'; more detail below.

It is unclear why such an unsustainable level of growth beginning mid-1928 continued for more than a year; perhaps a method similar to 'lag-lead' was in play; if so, it eventually put an end to 'irrational exuberance', with calamitous consequences. An amusing (rotated) graphic of the zig-zag behavior around the crash shows the log-scaled average bouncing diametrically inside a circle as if obeying some law-of-reflection!

Next, let's examine events around the crash of 1987, one of considerably shorter duration; the crossover occurred again well before the event (see below); the upward trend resumed quickly as if nothing had happened, albeit at a slower pace.

Finally, the 'sell' crossovers prior to the down-turn in this 2008 crisis were not unique using a 30-day averaging window; however, the crossover at up-turn did coincide with the very bottom of the average.

A long view of the DOW's activity is provided below using an 800-day averaging window; the log-scale data (in blue) and the 'lag-lead' signed residuals (in magenta) have been rescaled to fit within the same plot.

The major downturns could still be avoided at this longer horizon - except the (short) 1987 crash. Excessive growth with slope beyond a certain value on this logarithmic scale seems to (eventually) induce 'corrections'; the 'boom' then 'bust' syndrome in action. Growth after the 2008 'subprime' debacle does appear sustainable.

Variations in window length shed some light into strategies employed by investors, albeit in 'long' or 'short' trading; patterns may emerge - particularly at higher data granularity than available here - in what after all has always been a complex mixture of factors (political, financial, emotional, etc.) baked into the dynamics of a given equity. Whether the data timeline itself is sufficient to decouple these factors is the ultimate puzzle.

As an example, Apple stock analysis using 'doubled' windows (see below) gives an inkling of the many and varied investor horizons - from a jittery 50-day window outcome suggesting a very active traders, to a smooth 400-day outlook typical of a 'buy and hold' approach - at least in this century.

